

Analysis of Screening Mammography in a Tertiary Health Facility in Birnin Kebbi, Northwest Nigeria

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Abstract

Breast cancer is the most frequently diagnosed cancer in women worldwide and the leading cause of cancer death in both developed and developing countries. Mammography is a highly effective and widely used imaging modality for breast cancer screening and detection. This study is aimed at documenting the mammographic patterns of 92 females who had screening mammography at Federal Medical Centre Birnin Kebbi. The study was conducted in the department of radiology, Federal Medical Centre Birnin Kebbi from January, 2020 to December, 2023. The sociodemographic data and clinical history of the participants were obtained using a mammographic patient information form consisting of variables such as age, occupation, age at menarche, last menstrual period, marital status, parity, age at menopause, family history of breast cancer, previous breast surgery, use of contraceptives, previous mammography, biopsy and use of hormonal replacement therapy. A total of 92 females had screening mammography. All the participants had mediolateral (MLO) and craniocaudal (CC) views with additional views in selected participants. The mammograms were acquired on digital mammographic films and reported by two consultant radiologists, independently in different sessions. The findings were assigned and categorized using BI-RADS classification method. The participant's ages ranged from 40 to 68 years with a mean of 53.8 ± 9.1 years. Sixty-three (68.5%) had normal mammograms; the abnormal findings were: axillary lymph nodes 12 (13.0%), benign breast masses 10 (10.9%), parenchymal architectural distortion 4 (4.3%) and macro-calcifications 3 (3.3%). No breast masses with malignant features were seen. Majority of the participants for screening mammography were found to have normal mammograms; this indicates that the burden of breast disease is low in the study area. This study sheds light on the patterns and demographics of mammographic screening in Birnin Kebbi, northwest Nigeria, indicating a moderate participation rate, with a mammography prevalence of 31.5% among women who were screened.

Keywords: Analysis breast cancer, mammography, screening

1.0 Introduction

Breast cancer is the most frequently diagnosed cancer in women worldwide and the leading cause of cancer death in both developed and developing countries.^[1, 2] According to global cancer observatory (GLOBOCAN 2020), breast cancer is the most prevalent cancer among women in Africa, with approximately 186,598 new cases and 85,787 deaths reported annually.^[3]

Mammography is a highly effective and widely used imaging modality for breast cancer

screening and detection.^[4] Mammography screening allows for the early detection of breast cancer, which helps reduce mortality from breast cancer, particularly in women aged 50 – 69 years.^[5] Apart from low-dose mammography and contrast enhanced mammography, other newer imaging technologies for breast cancer screening include tomosynthesis, automated whole breast ultrasound (AWBUS), molecular imaging and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).^[6] Optimal breast cancer screening will require a personalized approach, with selective application of screening technologies best suited to the

individual's age, risk and breast density.^[6] The American Cancer Society (ACS) recommends annual mammography screening for women aged 40 to 54 years because it significantly reduces the risk of being diagnosed with advanced breast cancer compared to biennial screening.^[7] Women over the age of 55 years can opt for biennial screening. The ACS does not set a cut-off age for breast cancer screening, but acknowledges that women aged 75 years and older who are in good health and have an expected lifespan of 10 years or more may benefit from ongoing mammography screening.^[8,9] However, screening can be done earlier in those who are at an increased risk of breast cancer such as those with strong family history of breast cancer or who had history of radiotherapy to the chest wall.^[10] Mammography has limitations, and some researchers believe that the benefits do not always outweigh the risks. The sensitivity of mammography varies greatly, from 98% in women with fatty breast parenchyma to 36% in women with dense breasts.^[11, 12]

Women who have annual mammograms may still present with malignancies discovered only by physical breast examination. False-positive rates in breast cancer screening using mammography are a significant limitation as well because they lead to unnecessary biopsies and high call-back rates, which increases costs, radiation exposure and patient anxiety.^[13]

Breast density is an important variable that can change the sensitivity of mammography in the screening populations. Mammographic density is commonly measured using breast imaging reporting and data system (BI-RADS) recommendations from the American College of Radiologists (ACR).^[14] The 4th edition of the ACR BI-RADS guidelines relies on the percentage of fibroglandular tissue within the total breast using craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique views. Breasts with glandular densities of <25%, 25%–50%, 50%–75%, and >75% were assigned a BI-RADS density value of 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively. However, in the 5th edition, the percentage system was redefined with an emphasis on the possibility of having an obscured lesion. The categories were defined as follows: category A: almost entirely fat; category B: scattered fibroglandular densities; category C: heterogeneously dense; and category D: extremely dense.^[15, 16] The rate of breast cancer screening in Sub-Saharan Africa is very low,

which indicates the need for targeted intervention to reduce the burden of breast cancer and improve survivorship.^[17] The study is aimed at documenting the mammographic patterns of female participants who had screening mammography at Federal Medical Centre Birnin Kebbi using the ACR BI-RADS.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of study area

Federal Medical Centre is a government-owned tertiary healthcare facility located in Birnin Kebbi, the capital city of Kebbi state. It provides comprehensive medical services, including specialist consultations, surgery, radiology, maternity care and emergency services. As a tertiary centre, it serves not only Birnin Kebbi but also surrounding areas, offering both inpatient and outpatient care. FMC is instrumental in healthcare training and research, contributing to medical education in the region. It lies between latitude 12.4539° N and longitude 4.1975° E.

2.2 Study population, Sample collection and Processing

A total of 92 female clients were referred to the department of radiology, Federal Medical Centre Birnin Kebbi for screening mammography from January, 2020 to December, 2023. All the participants filled a mammographic patient information form consisting of variables such as age, occupation, age at menarche, last menstrual period, marital status, parity, age at menopause, family history of breast cancer, previous breast surgery, use of contraceptives, previous mammography, biopsy and use of hormonal replacement therapy. The examination was performed with a Siemens mammodiagnost machine with model number 1125314; serial number 12856 manufactured in Germany, June, 2010. All participants had Mediolateral (MLO) and Craniocaudal (CC) views taken. Additional views were occasionally obtained in some of the participants. The mammograms were acquired on digital mammographic films. The mammograms were reported by two consultant radiologists, independently in different sessions and the findings were assigned and categorized using BI-RADS classification method. The density classifications are: BI-RADS 1: Breast almost entirely fatty; BI-RADS 2: Scattered fibroglandular pattern; BI-RADS 3:

Heterogeneous dense pattern and BI-RADS 4: Homogenous dense pattern. The assessment categories of findings are as follows: BI-RADS 0: Inconclusive study; BI-RADS 1: Normal study, BI-RADS 2: Benign findings, BI-RADS 3: Probably benign findings; BI-RADS 4: Suspicious lesion, BI-RADS 5: Highly suspicious lesion and BI-RADS 6: known biopsy

The participant's biodata and the acquired mammograms were retrieved from the departmental archive. All the recorded variables and the reported mammograms were analysed using statistical software (SPSS) version 25. All screening mammograms of participants aged 40 years and above were included in the study because the risk of developing breast cancer typically increases with age, and screening mammography is more effective and commonly recommended for women in this age group. Breast cancer screening guidelines generally starts at age 40, as the breast tissue becomes less dense with age, making mammograms more accurate and beneficial in detecting abnormalities. Mammograms acquired from participants less than 40 years were excluded because younger women tend to have denser breast tissue, which can reduce the effectiveness of mammograms in detecting cancer. Additionally, the incidence of breast cancer is lower in this age group, making routine screening less beneficial. Those with previous surgical interventions were also excluded from the study to avoid confounding factors, as prior surgeries (e.g., mastectomies or lumpectomies) can affect mammogram results.

2.3 Ethical Approval and Consent to Participate

The study was approved by the Health Research and Ethics Committee of the Federal Medical Centre Birnin Kebbi, with the Ethical clearance code (FMC/BK/HP/045/P/517/VOL.IV/064). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, and the guidelines for teaching and research set by the Committee were followed rigorously.

2.4 Data analysis

The data was entered into Microsoft Excel 2013. Descriptive statistics were used to determine frequencies and were expressed as percentages.

3.0 Results

A total of 92 screening mammograms were evaluated during the study period. The participant's ages ranged from 40 to 68 years with a mean of 53.8 ± 9.1 years. The 61 – 70 years group constituted the highest group (28.3%) and the least was 46 – 50 years group (10.9%) as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of age groups of the participants

Age group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
40 – 45	24	26.1
46 – 50	10	10.9
51 – 55	17	18.5
56 – 60	15	16.3
61 – 70	26	28.3
Total	92	100.0

All the participants presented for screening mammography with no clinical symptoms. Sixty-three (68.5%) had normal mammograms; the abnormal findings were: benign axillary lymph nodes 12 (13.0%), benign breast masses 10 (10.9%), parenchymal architectural distortion 4 (4.3%) and lucent-centred macro-calcifications 3 (3.3%) as shown in Table 2 below. No breast masses with malignant features were seen.

Table 2: Mammographic features of the participants

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Normal	63	68.5
Architectural distortion	4	4.3
Breast mass	10	10.9
Lucent-centred macro-calcifications	3	3.3
Benign axillary lymph nodes	12	13.0
Total	92	100.0

Plate 1: Mediolateral oblique views of both breasts showing lucent-centred macro-calcifications more marked on the right breast

Plate 2: Mediolateral oblique views of both breasts showing bilateral benign axillary lymph nodes

Sixty-three (68.5%) had BI-RADS 1 category, four (4.3%) had BI-RADS 0 while 25 (27.2%) had BI-RADS 2 category. The breast densities were categorized as entirely fatty; BIRADS 1 category, seen in 44 participants (47.8%), scattered fibroglandular; BIRADS 2 category,

seen in 16 participants (17.4%), heterogeneous dense parenchyma; BIRADS 3 category seen in 30 participants (32.6%) and extremely dense breast seen in 2 participants (2.2%). See Table 3

Table 3: Breast densities of the study participants

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Entirely fatty	44	47.8
Scattered fibroglandular	16	17.4
Heterogeneously dense	30	32.6
Extremely dense	2	2.2
Total	92	100.0

In the study, a significant majority of participants were identified as Hausa (65.2%) and predominantly Muslim (68.5%). This is represented in figure 1. Educational backgrounds varied, with most participants having completed secondary (43.5%) or tertiary education (31.5%), as illustrated in figure 2. Additionally, over half of the participants (58.7%) reported no history of contraceptive use. Among those who had used contraceptives, implanon was the most common method, utilized by 19.6% of users, as illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 2: Distribution of participants according to their level of Western Education

Figure 3: Distribution of use of different forms of contraceptive methods among the participants

4.0 Discussion

Mammography is the main imaging modality for early detection of breast cancer. The purpose of screening mammography is to detect breast cancer prior to development of clinical symptoms, hopefully at earlier and more easily treatable stage.^[18]

In this study, the mammographic findings of 92 participants who presented for screening mammography were evaluated, contributing to the body of evidence on the demographic factors influencing mammography uptake in the region. This study found that the highest frequency of screening occurred in the 61-70 age group (28.3%), while the 46-50 age group had the lowest frequency (10.9%). This is in contrast to the findings by Muhammad et al.^[19], who reported the highest frequency in the 40-44 years age group in Sokoto, northwest Nigeria. The variation in age distribution could be attributed to several factors, including differences in the population structure, awareness levels, or health policies between the regions. Additionally, older women may have more routine interaction with healthcare systems due to other age-related conditions, potentially explaining their higher participation in screening programs. Younger women, who may not perceive themselves to be at high risk, might be less inclined to seek out mammographic screening, reflecting a potential gap in targeted education and

awareness campaigns for women below 50 years of age.

Majority of the study population were married women; this is similar to the studies done by Muhammad et al.^[19] in Sokoto, northwest Nigeria, Mark et al.^[20] in Enugu, southeast Nigeria and Obajimi et al.^[21] in Ibadan southwest Nigeria. Marriage is often associated with greater health-seeking behaviour, possibly due to spousal encouragement or support. However, this finding contrasts with Elsie et al.^[22] in Uganda, where only 10% of the study population were married. The geographical and cultural differences may play a role here, as Uganda may have different societal norms regarding marriage or family structure. Furthermore, being married might provide women with more access to healthcare, particularly if they are financially supported by their spouses. On the other hand, single or unmarried women might prioritize healthcare differently, reflecting a potential area where public health interventions could focus on increasing access and awareness for non-married populations.

A key observation in this study was the low level of Western education among the study population, which likely contributed to poor health-seeking behaviour and a lack of awareness of cancer screening programs. Education is a critical factor in influencing health literacy and proactive

healthcare behaviours, including the use of preventive services like mammography. The association between low education levels and poor screening uptake has been consistently reported in other studies, such as those by Mark et al.^[20] and Akinola et al.^[22]. Without sufficient knowledge, many women may remain unaware of the importance of early breast cancer detection, or they may harbour misconceptions about the screening process, which hinders participation. The findings highlight the need for more robust health education programs targeting both formal and informal sectors to increase awareness and uptake of mammographic screening.

The study revealed that most of the participants had little or no knowledge about mammographic screening practices, which mirrors findings from Muhammad et al.^[19] in Sokoto. This underscores a significant gap in public health education in the region. The lack of knowledge about breast cancer screening is likely contributing to the low prevalence of mammographic screening, reported to be 31.5% in this study. To improve screening rates, targeted interventions aimed at educating women about the benefits of early detection and addressing common misconceptions about breast cancer screening are essential. Public awareness campaigns, community-based education, and integration of cancer screening into primary healthcare services could play a vital role in increasing participation in mammographic screening, particularly in rural or underserved areas.

This study found that the prevalence of screening mammography in Birnin Kebbi was 31.5% over the study period. A similar finding was observed by Muhammad et al.^[19] in Sokoto. The similarity in the prevalence of screening mammography between Birnin Kebbi likely stems from shared geographical location and socio-cultural practices. Both regions are part of northern Nigeria, where traditional beliefs and lower levels of education might hinder proactive health-seeking behaviours. This points to a regional issue that requires broader intervention strategies tailored to the cultural context of northern Nigeria. Regional healthcare policies should emphasize the importance of culturally appropriate health education and the provision of affordable screening services to ensure that women in these areas can access and benefit from early detection programs.

In this study, we found that 63 participants (68.5%) had normal mammographic findings, while 29 (31.5%) presented with abnormal findings. Among the abnormal cases, 25 (27.2%) were classified as benign, and 4 (4.3%) were inconclusive. This distribution underscores that most abnormalities detected in screening mammography are benign, which is consistent with findings from similar studies^[19,20]. However, the presence of inconclusive cases highlights the need for follow-up imaging or biopsy to ensure accurate diagnosis. The abnormal mammographic findings revealed no statistically significant association between ethnicity, occupation, parity and family history of breast cancer among the participants. This lack of correlation aligns with previous studies^[19,20] that suggest these demographic and reproductive factors may not have a direct influence on mammographic abnormalities in this context. It is possible that other variables, such as genetic predispositions or environmental factors, could play a more critical role in the incidence of abnormal findings, though further research is required to elucidate these relationships.

One key finding from our study was the significant association between breast density and participant age. Younger women exhibited higher breast density, while older women tended to have lower density. This inverse relationship is well-documented in the literature and is important because higher breast density can obscure mammographic findings, making it more challenging to detect abnormalities in younger women. Our study's results align with findings from Muhammad et al.^[19] and Mark et al.^[20], reinforcing the importance of considering age-related changes in breast tissue when interpreting mammograms.

The final BI-RADS (Breast Imaging-Reporting and Data System) categories of the study participants were as follows: 63 (68.5%) fell under BI-RADS category 1, which indicates a normal mammogram; 4 participants (4.3%) were classified under BI-RADS 0, indicating that additional imaging evaluation was needed; and 25 participants (27.2%) were categorized as BI-RADS 2, which suggests benign findings. Our findings are consistent with studies by Muhammad et al.^[19] in Sokoto and Awosanya et al.^[23] in Lagos, both of which reported BI-RADS 1 as the most common mammographic finding. However, Akinola et al.^[22] in a South-Western Nigerian study reported a predominance of BI-RADS 2

findings, indicating benign abnormalities as the most frequent outcome in their population. These regional variations in BI-RADS categories may reflect differences in screening protocols, population demographics, or healthcare accessibility.

Our study identified a low prevalence of positive family history of breast cancer, with only 5 participants (5.4%) reporting such a history. This is in line with findings from Muhammad et al. [19] in Sokoto and Obajimi et al. [21] in Ibadan, both of which also reported low rates of family history. The relatively low awareness of familial risk factors may be attributed to a general lack of awareness about breast cancer and its hereditary implications in the population. This highlights the need for more extensive public education campaigns to improve understanding of breast cancer risk factors, including family history, and to promote regular screening practices. The lack of awareness and low reporting of family history might also be due to underreporting or insufficient knowledge about family medical histories among participants.

5.0 Conclusion

This study sheds light on the patterns and demographics of mammographic screening in Birnin Kebbi, northwest Nigeria, indicating a moderate participation rate, with a mammography prevalence of 31.5% among women who were screened. The highest screening participation was among older women (ages 61-70), while younger women had notably lower engagement, suggesting gaps in awareness and risk perception. Additionally, the findings showed that 68.5% of the mammograms were normal, and most abnormalities detected were benign. The low levels of education and awareness about breast cancer screening were also notable, pointing to a critical need for targeted education and outreach. Cultural and demographic factors, including marital status and family history, were identified as influencing healthcare-seeking behaviours, though no significant association was found between these factors and abnormal mammographic findings. These results underscore the value of mammography in identifying benign versus potentially suspicious findings and emphasize the importance of routine screenings and follow-ups, especially for younger women with higher breast density.

6.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, it is recommended that government and healthcare policymakers implement targeted breast cancer awareness programs specifically for younger women (under 50) and single or unmarried women to address the low screening participation observed in these groups. Integrating mammographic screening into routine primary healthcare services could significantly expand access, especially in rural and underserved areas. Additionally, comprehensive health education initiatives should be developed to promote the importance of early screening, with particular emphasis on women with limited formal education. These programs would help raise awareness of the benefits of early detection and the risks associated with delayed diagnosis.

To address socio-cultural barriers, culturally appropriate outreach programs should be prioritized in Northern Nigeria to encourage health-seeking behaviours while respecting local beliefs. Subsidized or low-cost mammographic screenings would also increase participation among women from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. Furthermore, healthcare providers should receive training on follow-up protocols to improve outcomes for cases needing further imaging or biopsies, thereby reducing inconclusive diagnoses and enabling timely treatment. Finally, educating women about family history as a risk factor for breast cancer is essential for empowering them to take proactive screening measures based on hereditary risk.

7.0 Acknowledgements

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8.0 Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest among the authors involved in the study.

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